

Figure 10 — Cascade mechanism: endogenous trends → unstable correlation

Price paths of 3 independent Preisach-MHTAR series

Rolling trend direction — periods of same sign = synchronisation

Rolling R^2 — spikes coincide with synchronised trend episodes above

